

Solute-Solvent Interactions in Solutions of Sodium Formate in Water and Aqueous Ethyl Formate

R. L. BLOKHRA and P. C. VERMA

Chemistry Department, Himachal Pradesh University, Simla-171 005

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Solute-solvent interaction in solutions of sodium formate in water and aqueous ethyl formate (5% by weight) has been deduced from the values of the limiting apparent molar volume, ϕ_v^0 , the B-coefficient of the Jones-Dole equation and from conductance studies at different concentrations and at different temperatures. It is found that the salt behaves as structure breaker in water and as structure promoter in case of aqueous ethyl formate.

SOLUTE-solvent interaction studies have been a subject of interest among physical chemists for the last two decades¹⁻⁶. The inference regarding the interactions is derived either from molar volume studies or viscosity studies or conductance studies or from all these properties^{7,8} together. Literature is full of such studies in pure solvents but investigations in mixed solvents are scanty. The studies in mixed solvents have never been undertaken in solutions where there is a similarity in ions of the salt and the solvent molecules. The present work was undertaken with the object of knowing the nature of solute-solvent interactions in such system from the molar volume, viscous flow and conductance data of sodium formate in water and aqueous ethyl formate. Sodium formate has been found to have negligible solubility in the formate and we carried out measurements in aqueous ethyl formate having water content enough to have solution of sufficient concentration in the salt.

Experimental

Sodium formate was used after usual purification⁹. Ethyl formate was dried over CaO and was distilled before use. The specific conductance, viscosity, density of ethyl formate at 25° is 3.4×10^{-7} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹, 0.00363 P and 0.91561 g.ml⁻¹ respectively. These are in good agreement with the literature values¹⁰. Water of conductivity 10^{-8} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ was used for making aqueous solutions and 5% (by weight) of aqueous ethyl formate. All solutions of the electrolytes were prepared by weight and the conversion of the molality into molarity was carried out by the expression given elsewhere¹¹. The density measurements, viscosity measurements and conductance measurements were carried out by the method described earlier¹²⁻¹³. All measurements except of viscosity were made in the water bath which was placed in an air thermostat having fluctuations always below 0.02°. In case of viscosity, measurements were carried out in air thermostat having temperature fluctuations of the order 0.05°.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volume, ϕ_v , is calculated from the density data by using the equation¹⁴

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_0 - d)}{m d d_0} + \frac{M_2}{d} \quad \dots (1)$$

where ϕ_v represents the molar volume of the electrolyte, d the density of the solution, d_0 the density of the solvent, m the molality of the solution and M_2 the molecular weight of the electrolyte. The density d , apparent molar volume ϕ_v , viscosity and the equivalent conductance Λ of the solutions at different concentrations for different systems are given in Table 1.

The density of the solutions can be represented by Root's equation¹⁵ :

$$\frac{d - d_0}{C} = A - B\sqrt{C} \quad \dots (2)$$

where A and B are the constants of the Root's equation. On plotting $d - d_0/C$ versus \sqrt{C} , a straight line should be obtained and we get straight line in each case. Values of A and B evaluated from the intercept and slope of the plots are given in Table 2.

The apparent molar volume has been found to vary linearly with the square root of the concentration and the data can be represented by the relation¹⁶ :

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S\sqrt{C} \quad \dots (3)$$

where ϕ_v^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume, and S is the experimental slope. Here ϕ_v^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interaction and for different systems the limiting apparent molar volume for sodium formate are given in Table 3.

TABLE 1—DENSITY, APPARENT MOLAR VOLUME, VISCOSITY AND EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE OF SODIUM FORMATE IN WATER AND 5% AQUEOUS ETHYL FORMATE.

Concentration C (mol. l ⁻¹)	Density d (g. ml ⁻¹)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (ml. mole ⁻¹)	Viscosity η (cp)	Equivalent conductance Λ (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)
<i>In Water</i>				
Temperature : 30°C, $d_0 = 0.99567$ g. ml ⁻¹ , $\Lambda_0 = 150.90$ ohm ⁻¹ cm ²				
0.00248	—	—	—	140.01
0.00869	—	—	—	127.02
0.01379	—	—	—	119.10
0.02105	—	—	—	115.02
0.03248	0.99706	25.32	0.805	109.14
0.06445	0.99841	25.62	0.810	101.95
0.12156	1.00078	25.81	0.817	95.31
0.18063	1.00322	26.33	0.827	—
0.23713	1.00533	26.54	0.835	—
0.33074	1.00929	26.95	0.848	—
0.42267	1.01293	27.31	0.863	—
Temperature : 35°C, $d_0 = 0.99406$ g. ml ⁻¹ , $\Lambda_0 = 166.50$ ohm ⁻¹ cm ²				
0.00302	—	—	—	154.02
0.00753	—	—	—	143.43
0.01405	—	—	—	135.43
0.01963	—	—	—	129.53
0.02957	0.99541	22.49	0.723	122.81
0.05486	0.99653	23.10	0.725	111.89
0.09872	0.99845	23.50	0.728	105.97
0.15603	1.00094	24.06	0.732	—
0.22238	1.00374	24.46	0.739	—
0.31933	1.00776	25.25	0.750	—
0.41469	1.01163	25.80	0.784	—

(Contd.)

(TABLE I CONTD.)

Concentration C (mol. l ⁻¹)	Density d (g. ml ⁻¹)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (ml. mole ⁻¹)	Viscosity η (cp)	Equivalent conductance Λ (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)
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Temperature : 40°C, $d_0 = 0.99224$ g. ml⁻¹, $\Lambda_0 = 178.70$ ohm⁻¹cm²

0.00301	—	—	—	164.12
0.00726	—	—	—	152.51
0.01383	—	—	—	143.75
0.02406	—	—	—	134.10
0.03821	0.99403	21.32	0.657	124.45
0.06827	0.99538	22.15	0.667	116.51
0.11371	0.99739	22.87	0.672	107.97
0.16605	0.99957	24.05	0.678	—
0.23423	1.00243	24.69	0.687	—
0.33756	1.00646	26.09	0.698	—
0.44493	1.01084	26.41	0.715	—

In 5% Aqueous Ethyl Formate

Temperature : 30°C, $d_0 = 0.99574$ g. ml⁻¹, $\Lambda_0 = 138.70$ ohm⁻¹cm²

0.00422	—	—	—	130.00
0.01716	—	—	—	121.00
0.03705	0.99785	11.12	0.903	—
0.03811	—	—	—	114.77
0.05336	—	—	—	107.00
0.08061	1.00011	13.89	0.926	97.47
0.11902	—	—	—	91.00
0.14220	1.00283	18.23	0.936	83.16
0.19802	1.00534	19.61	0.951	—
0.25713	1.00711	23.90	0.956	—
0.33756	1.01062	24.03	0.975	—
0.45661	1.01512	25.68	0.999	—

(Cont.)

(TABLE 1 CONTD.)

Concentration C (mol. l ⁻¹)	Density d (g. ml ⁻¹)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (ml. mole ⁻¹)	Viscosity η (cp)	Equivalent conductance Λ (ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻²)
Temperature : 35°C, $d_o = 0.99427$ g. ml ⁻¹ , $\Lambda_o = 156.90$ ohm ⁻¹ cm ²				
0.00491	—	—	—	145.00
0.01588	0.99519	10.16	—	—
0.01822	—	—	—	135.00
0.03062	—	—	—	129.00
0.05062	—	—	—	121.00
0.06250	0.99745	17.22	—	—
0.07384	0.99758	—	0.820	114.82
0.09610	—	—	—	108.00
0.11222	0.99945	22.00	0.821	—
0.14062	—	—	—	98.00
0.17222	1.00150	26.18	0.833	—
0.25978	1.00447	28.91	0.847	—
0.37210	1.00654	35.34	0.860	—
0.46241	1.00767	39.26	0.867	—

TABLE 2—VALUES OF PARAMETERS A AND B OF ROOT'S EQUATION.

System	Temperature (°C)	A (g. l. mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻²)	B (g. l ^{3/2} mol ^{-3/2} cm ⁻²)
Sodium formate in water	30	0.0436	0.0040
	35	0.0469	0.0071
	40	0.0496	0.0100
Sodium formate in 5% aqueous ethyl formate	30	0.0630	0.0329
	35	0.0420	0.0487

TABLE 3—VALUES OF ϕ_v^0 OF SODIUM FORMATE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN WATER AND AQUEOUS ETHYL FORMATE.

System	Temperature (°C)	ϕ_v^0 (ml. mol ⁻¹)
Sodium formate in water	30	24.40
	35	21.30
	40	18.25
Sodium formate in 5% aqueous ethyl formate	30	5.00
	35	5.25

The greater magnitude of ϕ_0^0 in case of water suggests that the solute-solvent interaction is greater in case of water. Further, Table 3 shows that it decreases with increasing temperature in case of water and increases with temperature in case of aqueous ester.

Data on viscosity was analysed with the help of the Jones-Dole equation¹⁷ :

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots (4)$$

where η is the viscosity of the solution, η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent, C is the molar concentration and A and B are constants characteristic of the solute electrolyte. A coefficient represents the contribution from interionic electrostatic force¹⁸. The B coefficient is said to be a measure of the effective hydrodynamic volume of the solvated ions¹⁹ and to denote the order or disorder introduced by the ions into the solvent structure. The values of A and B of equation (4) are determined from the intercept and slope of the straight line plots of $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} . These values for different solutions are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—JONES-DOLE PARAMETERS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES.

System	Temperature (°C)	A mol ^{-1/2} cm ^{3/2}	B mol ⁻¹ cm ³
Sodium formate in water	30	0.008	0.166
	35	0.01	0.181
	40	0.01	0.183
Sodium formate in 5% aqueous ethyl formate	30	-0.035	0.258
	55	-0.020	0.243

In the Jones-Dole equation, A is a calculable parameter and is similar for all 1:1 electrolytes. The A -parameter has been found to be 0.0093 ± 0.0009 . The positive temperature coefficient of B -parameter, dB/dT , suggest that the salt behaves like a structure breaker²⁰ in case of water.

In case of solutions in aqueous ethyl formate the negative values of A has been obtained. However, the negative magnitude of A cannot be interpreted on the basis of Falkenhagen theory²¹ and negative A values has been obtained in most of the cases involving mixed solvents^{22,23}. The negative temperature coefficient of B , dB/dT suggest that the salts behave as a structure maker in the aqueous ester.

The limiting equivalent conductance of sodium formate in water and aqueous ethyl formate at different

temperature is evaluated from Onsager's plots²⁴, and with the help of Owen method²⁵. The limiting equivalent conductance, Λ_0 , along with the Walden product, $\Lambda_0\eta_0$, is given in Table 5.

TABLE 5—LIMITING EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE, Λ_0 , WALDEN PRODUCT, $\Lambda_0\eta_0$, FOR SODIUM FORMATE IN

Temperature (°C)	Λ_0 (Owen) (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	Λ_0 (Onsager) (ohm ⁻¹ cm ²)	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$
<i>Water</i>			
30	150.9	159.0	1.208
35	166.5	178.5	1.203
40	178.7	191.5	1.172
<i>5% Aqueous Ethyl Formate</i>			
30	138.7	139.0	1.269
35	156.9	156.0	1.272

The structural effects on the conductance of ions in solutions can be derived by a comparison of the Walden product (conductance-viscosity products) at different temperatures²⁰. The negative temperature coefficient of the Walden product in water suggest that the salt behaves like a structure breaker in case of water and structure promotor in case of aqueous ethyl formate. These conclusions are in agreement with those derived from viscosity measurements.

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